

The Importance of Learning Non Verbal Communication

Yaqubjonova Ro‘zixon Mirkomil qizi¹

¹ASIFL, The Department of English and literature, teacher

Abstract:

In modern era, scientists are interested in the importance of non verbal communication. Due to, gestures mean differently in every nation and cultures. In this article we focus the importance of learning gestures.

Keywords: verbal and nonverbal communication, facial expressions, gestures.

Human speech activity is closely connected with all aspects of human consciousness. Speech is a powerful factor of a person's mental maturity, formation as a person. Under the influence of speech, views, beliefs, intellectual, spiritual and aesthetic feelings are formed, will and character are formed. With the help of speech, all mental processes related to cognition become free and controlled. Therefore, speech is a mental process related to cognition, which consists of a combination of sounds pronounced and heard by a person, and at the same time has a meaning and content expressed through a system of written signs corresponding to these sounds. As a means of communication, speech appears simultaneously as a source of information and as a means of interaction with the interlocutor. As the great poet Saadi said: “We don't know whether you have a mind or not, whether you are great or small, until you say a word.”

Verbal (speech) communication includes: the meaning and essence of words, phrases. The main place is occupied by the accuracy of the use of the word, its expression and universality, sounds, pronunciation of words, tone expression and essence. Sound phenomena in speech: speech speed, pitch modulation, sound tone, speech weight, sound quality, tone, clarity. Expression of sound quality: unique special sounds: laughter, hiccups, cries, whispers, sighs, etc.; disjunctive sounds are coughs; insignificant sounds - pauses, as well as nasalization sounds – “hmm, hmm”, “ehh-ehh-ehh”, “oh-oh-oh” and others.

According to research, in the daily act of human communication, words - 7%, sounds and expressions - 38%, non-verbal interaction - 53%. As the Publicist says: "we talk through our voice, we talk through our whole body." Facial expressions, gaze, gestures are the most informative means of non-verbal communication. Forehead, eyebrows, mouth, eyes, nose, chin - these parts of the face represent the main human emotions: emigration, anger, joy, surprise, fear, hatred, happiness, interest, sadness and others. Although non-verbal communication is different in different countries, the emotions shown through facial expressions are the same all over the world. On the negotiations or a business trip abroad, everyone should definitely learn the meaning of the gestures of the country they are going to. During the meeting, using unfamiliar gestures can upset the interlocutor, various misunderstandings may arise, and as a result, the interlocutor's opinion will be negative towards that person, and in some cases, this will cause serious negotiations to be broken. English people often use non-verbal communication, i.e. gestures, to express their thoughts and feelings. With the back of the "V" facing the person, the V shape means "two", "peace" or "victory". However, if the hand is turned so that the back of the hand is facing the other person, it is a very rude gesture. This type of V sign is similar to the middle finger gesture explained below, but is often more derisive than aggressive and is slightly more offensive. Next sign: A hand clenched into a fist with the thumb sharply raised is considered a curse. To non-verbally emphasize the confidential nature of information, the British use their index finger to poke their nose. So, it is crucial to learn other nations' gestures in order to make correct communication with other people.

References

1. V.Vositov (2022).Classification theory of Turkic borrowings. "International journal of world languages" Scientific Journal, Tom-1, 11-14
2. G.Ibragimova (2021). Structural and Semantic Properties of Parenthesis in English Essays. "International Journal of Multireligious Understanding." Scientific Journal, Tom-8, 163-168
3. B.Otajonov, A.Ismoilov (2023) "Nominative field of English and Uzbek means expressing the concept of "Mouth"" Organization Committee-153 p
4. B.Otajonov(2023) "The nominative field of means expressing the concept of "Mouth" in English and Uzbek". "Journal of Language and linguistics" Scientific Journal, Tom-6, 171-183
5. Q.Umirzaqov (2012) "Ellipsis in complex sentences as a grammatical and semantic phenomenon in different languages" Филология мэсэлэлэри, Баку, Озарбайжон Республикаси, Том-6, 321-323
6. I.Abdullayev(2023) "Characteristics of mutual function of parts of speech in English and Uzbek", Евразийский журнал академических исследований, Том-3, 7-10
7. G.Zaynobiddinova(2019) "The fifteen stages of teaching number for pupils", "Science and education in the modern challenges of the xxi centure"
8. R.M.Yaqubjonova (2023) "Language and culture in english classrooms: greetings, ways of expressing politeness" Наука и инновация, Том-1, 66-68
9. Sh. Xamraqulova (2024) " Unique features of toponymic slangs in English language" SCHOLAR Том-2, 87-94
10. M.Abduraimova (2022)"The Importance of Teaching English at Early Age in Pre School-Education" Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, Том-6, 55-60
11. D.Tuxtasinova(2022) "How to teach english language medical engineering specialty students" International Scientific Conference" Innovative Trends In Science, Practice And Education" Том-1, 157-162

12. N.Boltaboyeva, N.Latipova (2022) “National And Cultural Variety Of Phraseological Unit Of The English Language.” Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka, Tom-2
13. Sh. Umirzaqova (2022) “Using language experience approach in training TFL.” Scientific Ideas Of Young Scientists | Pomysly Naukowe Mlodych Naukowcow Научные Идеи Молодых Ученых Tom-6, 76-79